

Evaluation Report

COSMO5.0_clm6/9

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Short summary

The regional climate model COSMO-CLM is a community model (www.clm-community.eu). In close collaboration with the COSMO-consortium the model is further developed by the community members for climate applications. One of the tasks of the community is to give a recommendation on the model version and to evaluate the model's performance.

The COPAT (Coordinated Parameter Testing) initiative is a voluntary community effort to carry out model simulations systematically by different institutions in order to test new model options and to find a satisfactory model setup for hydrostatic climate simulations over Europe. We will present the COPAT method used to achieve the latest recommended model version of COSMO-CLM (COSMO5.0_clm6).

The simulations cover the EURO-CORDEX domain at two spatial resolutions 0.44° and 0.165°. They are forced by ERAinterim data for the time period of 1979-2000. Interpolated forcing data has been prepared once to ensure that all participating groups used identical forcing. The evaluation of each individual run has been performed for the time period 1981-2000 by using ETOOL and ETOOL-VIS. These tools have been developed within the community to evaluate standard COSMO-CLM output in comparison to observations provided by EOBS and CRU.

The COPAT procedure was structured into 6 phases. In the **Pre-Phase** a group of institutions volunteered to contribute, a wiki has been setup, the forcing has been prepared and reference simulations at DKRZ have been performed. Furthermore, evaluation measures had been fixed and the necessary tools developed. In **Phase 1** all participating institutions performed a reference run on their individual computing platforms and tested the influence of single model options on the results afterwards. Derived from the results of Phase 1 the most promising options were used in combinations in the second phase (**Phase 2**). These first two phases of COPAT consist of more than 70 simulations with a spatial resolution of 0.44°. Based on the best setup identified in Phase 2, a calibration of eight tuning parameters has been carried out following Bellbrat et al. (2012) in **Phase 3**. A final simulation with the calibrated parameters has been set up in **Phase 4** at a higher resolution of 0.165°. The results were compared to previous model versions. The new model version COSMO5.0_clm6 led to the same or better results and therefore had been defined in the **Final Phase** as the new recommended model version of the community.

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1. Introduction

The model version COSMO4.8_clm19 was the last official and recommended version of COSMO-CLM (2012) and had been used by the members of the CLM-Community¹ for a variety of regional climate investigations. This version had been substantially evaluated and showed an excellent performance comparable with other state of the art regional climate models at that time. It had been used to regionalize several global climate change scenarios for Europe and Africa, but also for other continents. These model simulations are performed within the CORDEX framework and are among simulations by other RCM the basis for the Fifth Assessment Report (AR5) of the IPCC.

In 2013 a new model version was build up, bringing together the model extension of the CLM-Community with the operational standard version of the weather forecast model COSMO of the Deutscher Wetterdienst (DWD). This reunification of the two model branches resulted in the new model version COSMO-CLM 5.0 (CCLM 5.0). The new version offered a number of principal improvements and extensions. But their influence on the climate time scale had to be evaluated.

The previous reunified model version COSMO4.0 had been extensively evaluated by the BTU Cottbus in the context of the BMBF-funded overall coordination of the CLM-Community. Due to the funding by the BMBF ended in 2012 the DWD took over the coordination of the CLM-Community and an extensive evaluation of further model versions was no longer funded. This led to a big challenge for the community. By regulations in the community documents the working group “Evaluation” is responsible to suggest a new model version to be a recommended one. The evaluation had to be distributed between the community members. The challenge was to define a procedure to be able to make simulations comparable carried out at different computing machines.

The following chapters document the overall concept of the evaluation project and show the results of the final evaluation runs and the quality of this model version with respect to a number of climate quantities.

¹ <https://www.clm-community.eu/>

All results presented here are valid for the COSMO-CLM subversion 5.0_clm6. CLM-Community members vote on the new recommended COSMO-CLM during the community meeting at the Assembly in Luxembourg in 2015 and COSMO5.0_clm6 became the new recommended version of the CLM-Community. Afterwards further extensions and bug corrections have led to further subversions: clm7: adapted output formats (attributes of vertical coordinates for nesting purposes), clm8: bugfix for format of time variable (for simulations longer than 68 years), bug fix for negative runoff for itype_evsl=2, clm9: itype_evsl=3 bugfixes (domain decomposition), bugfix to avoid restart problems in certain configurations, new (untested) parametrization of bare soil evaporation itype_evsl=4, clm10: new spectral nudging option, clm11: addon to have netCDF formatted restart files , clm12: additional diagnostical variables: averaged wind speeds, wind direction frequency, etc., clm13: bugfix of the new diagnostics, clm14: bugfix of output dimensions of T_SO, clm15: precision of time and time_bnds variables changed, clm16: bug correction for netCDF restart files, clm17: additional emissions scenarios for CMIP6.

These extensions are not considered by the evaluation runs presented here. But it had been verified that the extensions, and bugfixes to that extensions, plus the netCDF formatted restart files of the subversions beyond the clm6 subversion do not lead to changes in the climatological means.

The results and conclusions of this report are therefore also valid for the latest CCLM subversion 5.0_clm17 (which was the basis for COSMO5.1 in 2015). This version was used for CORDEX downscaling simulations.

2. COPAT – a procedure towards a recommended model version

The whole COPAT initiative was structured in 6 phases as depicted in *Figure 1*. In the **Pre-Phase** general aspects of the simulation strategy were discussed, the model domain for the sensitivity studies was defined, uniform forcing data were generated, a list of potential namelist-parameters (model configuration) to be tested were selected and reference runs with the old and the new model version were performed on the finer evaluation and the coarser sensitivity study grid. The central part of the COPAT activities consisted of a large number of sensitivity studies with differing simulation configurations and can be divided into 4 phases.

Figure 1: General COPAT-procedure including tasks per phase and the number of simulations performed in grey.

In **Phase 1** all participating institutions performed a reference run on their individual computing platforms if not using the computing resources from the DKRZ, where the reference runs have been performed (see Pre-Phase). In sensitivity runs the influence of single model option have been tested by changing only one parameter compared to the reference run. Derived from the results of Phase 1 the most promising options were used in combinations in the second phase (**Phase 2**). These first two phases of COPAT consist of more than 70 simulations with a spatial resolution of 0.44°. Based on the best setup identified in Phase 2 a calibration of eight tuning parameters has been carried out following Bellbrat et al. (2012) in **Phase 3**. A final simulation with the calibrated parameters has been performed in **Phase 4** at a higher resolution of 0.165°. The results were compared to previous model versions. The new model version COSMO5.0_clm6 led to the same or better results and therefore had been defined in the **Final Phase** as the new recommended model version of the community.

All Phases are described in detail within the following Sections 2.1.-2.6.

Figure 2: Principle of the simulation strategy within the COPAT-procedure.

Principle Simulation Setup Strategy within the COPAT-procedure

Based on the so called standard evaluation of the last recommended model version COSMO-CLM 4.8_clm19 (see Section 1) the following principle simulation strategy was selected to systematically investigate and demonstrate the effects of the new model version COSMO-CLM 5.0 and of a new optimized standard configuration for that version in climate mode (see Figure 2):

- Standard evaluation run of CCLM 4.8_clm19 on the standard evaluation domain with 0.165° resolution (see section 2.1) with the old recommended configuration for Central Europe (simulation-ID CON031).
- Transfer of this old standard evaluation run onto a 0.44° grid being used for all sensitivity studies (simulation-ID: CON431).
- Adaptation of the old standard configuration of CCLM 4.8_clm19 to the new model version CCLM 5.0. This simulation represents the reference run for all following sensitivity studies on the 0.44° grid (simulation-ID: CON502).
- Transfer of this reference run back to the standard evaluation domain (simulation-ID: CON052).
- Series of systematic sensitivity runs with different configurations of CCLM 5.0 (simulation-IDs: CON5XX, CON6XX) to find out a new optimized configuration for the new model version over Central Europe at 0.44° resolution. The detailed strategy for this phase is described in section 2.3.
- Final evaluation run with the new configuration on the 0.44° grid (simulation-ID: CON609).
- Transfer of this final configuration onto the standard evaluation domain and execution of a new standard evaluation run (simulation-ID: CON069).

An overview of different model versions, configurations, resolutions and simulations-IDs is given in Table 1.

Table 1: Simulation IDs for different model versions, grid resolutions and simulation configurations used in the COPAT initiative

Simulation-ID	Model Version	Grid Resolution	Configuration
CON031	4.8_clm19	0.165°	recommended standard configuration for 4.8_clm19
CON431	4.8_clm19	0.44°	as CON031
CON502	5.0_clm6	0.44°	standard configuration of 4.8 adapted to version 5.0
CON052	5.0_clm6	0.165°	as CON502
CON5XX, CON6XX	5.0_clm6	0.44°	varying configurations for sensitivity studies
CON609	5.0_clm6	0.44°	new selected standard configuration for 5.0_clm6
CON069	5.0_clm6	0.165°	as CON609
CON067	5.0_clm6	0.165°	as CON069 but without the tuning parameters selected by ETH (section 2.4)

The transfer of the old standard configuration of version 4.8_clm19 to the new model version 5.0 posed some problems and did not end up in a completely identical configuration and simulation. Further details are presented in section 2.1.

In the end, the three simulations CON031, CON052 and CON069 on the standard evaluation domain are used for the final analysis presented in this document in section 2.5 to demonstrate the effects and improvements of model version CCLM 5.0_clm6 and the new recommended model configuration for Central Europe.

2.1. Pre-Phase

Forming a group of people

As already stated before, the COPAT (Coordinated Parameter Testing) initiative is a voluntary community effort to carry out model simulations systematically by different institutions in order to test new model options and to find a satisfactory model setup for hydrostatic climate simulations over Europe. People from 10 different institutions (all member institutions of the CLM-Community) volunteered to take part in the COPAT-project and carry out and share necessary model simulations. All agreed to the coordinated effort to aim on a new recommended model version.

Setup a general strategy and a wiki

The general structure of the COPAT with the different Phases was defined in detail (see *Figure 1* and *Figure 2*). Additionally, a wiki was setup to provide all relevant information, input data and namelists² and share output data, figures and plots.

Definition of a list of relevant parameters to test

As already described in the introduction the new model version COSMO5.0 was bringing together the model extension of the CLM-Community with the operational standard version of the weather forecast model COSMO. The new version offered a number of principal improvements and extensions from the forecast developer group. The influence of these changes had to be systematically tested in the climate mode of the model. But not all changes and improvements of the model necessarily influence the model results. In a first step all changes from the former recommended model version to the new reunified model version COSMO5.0 had been listed. Together, experts from the CCLM-Community and the Numerical Weather Prediction (NWP) of DWD discussed the list of changes in the model and their potential influence on the model results. With respect of the long list of changes and the following sensitivity runs all parameters to be tested were prioritized. In this way in the following Phases of the COPAT-procedure first the parameters with highest priority had to be tested and all others would follow depending on available computing time and working capacity.

The list had been published in the community internal wiki where all participants of the COPAT could indicate the sensitivity runs they intended to perform.

Definition of the domain, time period and base setup

Domains: All simulations cover the European domain. The final model evaluation is performed for the simulation on the high resolution of 0.165°. To save computing power all sensitivity runs for the testing of single parameters, combined parameters and the tuning were carried out at the coarser resolution of 0.44° (see *Figure 1* and *Figure 2*). Domains and basic information on the setup configuration are given in *Table 2*.

Time Period: The simulations cover the time period from **1979 to 2000**. An exception are the tuning simulations. As a large number of simulations are needed, the tuning simulations have a length of five years only and cover the time period 1979-1983. For the analysis of the results and the influence of the different setups on the climate scale, the first two years have been left out. Therefore, the evaluation period is **1981-2000**.

² A list of externally specified parameters that control the configuration (setup) of an individual simulation

Table 2: Domains and basic information of the simulations at a spatial resolution of 0.44° (left column) and 0.165° (right column).

Basic configuration	0.44°	0.165°
pollon; pollat	-162.0°; 39.25°	-162.0°; 39.25°
dlon; dlat	0.44°	0.165°
startlon_tot	-33.9300°	-25.0475°
startlat_tot	-7.9720°	-22.1925°
ie_tot	132 grid cells	257 grid cells
je_tot	129 grid cells	271 grid cells
ke_tot	40 layers	40 layers
dt	300 s	150 s

Preparation of forcing data using int2lm

The application of the new model version CCLM 5.0 also required the usage of a new preprocessor (int2lm) version to provide modified or additional components of forcing data for this version. While the initial and lateral boundary data for the old standard evaluation (CON031) had been prepared by int2lm_1.10_clm9, int2lm_2.0_clm1 was used for the forcing data of all simulations with the new model version CCLM 5.0. In the new int2lm version the so called Cressman scheme, which had particularly been used for the interpolation of the SST from the coarse to the local grid in former versions, was replaced by a different scheme in the updated int2lm version. Together with the new preprocessor and model version the preparation of the external data files has also been updated. The forcing data for the old standard evaluation used the external data file *extp2_084_dwdstd_europe_0165.nc* generated by the WebPEP version 0.84. All new reference and sensitivity simulations on the 0.44° grid used *extp2_v160_test-CCLM5_europe_0440.nc* generated by EXTPAR v1.6_clm6. The main difference between these external data is the correction of wrong values for the plant cover parameters PLCOV_MIN (0.2) and PLCOV_MAX (0.5) which had been 10 times too large over the Sahara. The two final simulations on the standard evaluation grid (CON052, CON069) were performed with the external data file *external_parameter_comso5_0165_consortial.nc* generated by EXTPAR 2.0.2 (identical to file

extp2_v202_dwdritter_europe_0165.nc). The fields in the last two external data files are interpolated from the same global data sets, i.e. GLOBE for orography, GLC2000 for land use, FAO-DSMW for soil parameters, the look-up table of Ritter_2007 and MODIS dry & sat for the surface albedo, and differ therefore, in principle, only in their horizontal resolution.

The configuration of the namelist variables used to generate the initial and lateral boundary data for the reference run and the subsequent sensitivity studies with CCLM 5.0_clm6 on the 0.44° grid are summarized in the file *int2lm-config_for_CCLM5.0_044.tar*. The forcing data was only generated once at DKRZ and was uniformly used for all sensitivity studies by all participating groups. By this approach the risk was eliminated that deviations between simulations performed by different groups could have been caused by differences in the generation of the forcing data. Afterwards, the same configuration was used to generate the initial and lateral boundary conditions for the reference run and the final standard evaluation on the 0.165° grid. The respective listings of the namelist variables are given in the file *int2lm-config_for_CCLM5.0_0165.tar*. The only difference between the int2lm-settings for the reference run CON052 and the final evaluation run CON069 is in the namelist variable *itype_rootdp*, which had the value of 3 in CON052 and the value 4 in CON069.

Setup reference simulations at DKRZ

The first step of the evaluation strategy was to provide an appropriate reference simulation for all the succeeding sensitivity runs. For this purpose, the standard evaluation of CCLM 4.8_clm19 (CON031) was repeated on the 0.44° grid (CON431). The next step was to perform an equivalent simulation on both grids with CCLM 5.0 without any changes in the configuration of the namelist variables. These two runs should in an ideal case reproduce the results of the old model version on the corresponding grids. However, due to the correction of several bugs and the modification and extension of some process treatments between the two versions this was in principle not possible. In addition, the default values of some namelist variables had been changed from version 4.8 to version 5.0 so that the reproduction of the reference runs with CCLM_4.8 necessitates a corresponding adaptation of the settings for these parameters as listed in *Table 3*.

Table 3: Namelist variables of the reference configurations whose values had to be adapted in CCLM 5.0 to the settings in the CCLM 4.8 reference simulations due to modifications of the default settings in the new model version.

Namelist parameter	Default value in CCLM 5.0	Adapted value in CCLM 5.0 consistent with CCLM 4.8 reference simulations
securi	0.5	0.85
tkhmin, tkmmin	0.4	1.0
mu_rain	0	0.5
v0snow	25	20
itype_bbc_w	114	1
itype_fast_waves	2	1
l_diff_smag	TRUE	FALSE (variable not available in 4.8)
limpltkediff	TRUE	F ALSE (variable not available in 4.8)
itype_albedo	2	1

Due to additional namelist variables in CCLM 5.0, which enable either to expand parameterizations already implemented in the old model version or configure additional new parameterization, some unavoidable changes of the simulations results had to be expected and accepted. The concerned parameters are listed in *Table 4*.

Table 4: Values of new namelist variables introduced in CCLM 5.0 and their adequate or non-adequate representation in CCLM 4.8.

Namelist parameter	Value used in CCLM 5.0 reference simulations	Realization in or modified influence on CCLM 4.8 reference simulations
a_hsr a_stab	0.2 0	not available in 4.8, influence unclear due to general modifications in the turbulence scheme
rain_n0_factor	0.4	not available in 4.8, influence unclear due to modified formulation in sub-program src_gscp
thick_sc	25000	identical to fixed implementation in 4.8
y_vert_adv_dyn	impl2	identical to lva_impl_dyn=.TRUE.
y_scalar_advect	Bott2	erroneously assumed to be identical to yef_adv_qx = Bott_2 in 4.8 but it turned out after simulation had been finished that setting of lsl_adv_qs=.TRUE. cancels the setting of yef_adv_qx and activates semi-implicit advection scheme identical to y_scalar_advect=SL3_MF in 5.0
itype_aerosols	1	not available but identical to fixed treatment of aerosols in 4.8
l_diff_smag	FALSE	not available in 4.8, FALSE prevents Smagorinsky diffusion scheme from execution, no modification of results
limpltkediff	FALSE	replaces lturhor=FALSE in 4.8, no modification of results

With the modifications listed in *Table 3* and *Table 4* in CCLM_5.0 compared to namelist settings in CCLM 4.8 two new reference runs of CCLM 5.0_clm6 on the two grids - CON502 on 0.44° and CON052 on 0.165° grid - were performed on computer system “Blizzard” at DKRZ in Hamburg. CON502 serves as the reference run for all following sensitivity runs with modified configurations and CON052 for the final comparison with the old standard evaluation of CCLM 4.8 (CON031) and the new standard evaluation with an optimized configuration for CCLM 5.0 (CON069). The settings of the namelist variables for the two reference runs are summarized in the provided tar-files CON502_config.tar and CON052_config.tar.

Evaluation concept using ETOOL/ETOOL-VIS

The model results from sensitivity runs at 0.44° as well as from the final evaluation run at 0.165° spatial resolution have been evaluated based on gridded observations. The reference data from the gridded data set E-OBS (version 10.0) of the ENSEMBLES project and from the data set of the CRU (Climate Research Unit at the University of East Anglia) are used.

Analysis include the calculation of mean annual cycle of **biases**, the **standard deviation**, **temporal and spatial correlation**, **root mean squared error** and the **Brier Skill Score**. As the calculation of most of the measures is very common only the Brier Skill Score should be described in the box below.

The **Brier Skill Score (BSS)** is defined, e.g. von Storch and Zwiers (1999), by

$$BSS = 1 - \frac{\sigma_F^2}{\sigma_R^2},$$

where σ_F^2 and σ_R^2 represent the error variances of the "forecast" F (the time series of the modelled parameter from e.g. sensitivity run) and the "reference" R (the time series of the modelled parameter from the reference run).

The error variances are computed relative to the same predictand, in this case the respective time series of observed parameter within a certain time period.

By definition the Brier Skill Score can vary between $-\infty$ and $+1$. For the value 1 ($\sigma_F^2=0$) the forecast exactly matches the observations. Negative values indicate a better performance of the reference; positive values ($\sigma_F^2 < \sigma_R^2$) indicate an added value of the "forecast" in comparison to the reference.

Additionally, in the present study, a modified (symmetric) BSS is introduced with a range of -1 to 1 . Values from -1 to 0 indicate a better performance of the **reference** run, values between 0 and 1 indicate an added value for the parameter **modelled** with the modified setup. "0" means both setups, the modified and the reference run are of about the same quality; none of the simulations is closer to the observations than the other.

$$BSS_{\text{ext}} = \begin{cases} 1 - \frac{RMSE_{\text{mod}}^2}{RMSE_{\text{ref}}^2} & \text{for } RMSE_{\text{mod}} \leq RMSE_{\text{ref}} \\ \frac{RMSE_{\text{ref}}^2}{RMSE_{\text{mod}}^2} - 1 & \text{for } RMSE_{\text{ref}} < RMSE_{\text{mod}} \end{cases}$$

The results are evaluated for eight different sub-regions, shown in *Figure 3*. The exact definition of borders for these sub-regions is given in *Table 5*. For these sub-regions the climatologically means are calculated as area averages over all land points and are compared to corresponding reference data. The results of the evaluation are illustrated by **area plots** of annual means or sums for the whole domain and by **annual cycles** of the deviations from the observations and their potential uncertainty. Additionally, **Taylor-Plots** represent the spatial but also temporal correlation of the model output and reference data sets. They combine the correlation, the standard deviation and the root mean squared error in one figure.

Following variables are evaluated against the mentioned observational data set:

- 2 m air temperature: E-OBS
- 2 m maximum temperature: E-OBS
- 2 m minimum temperature: E-OBS
- 2 m diurnal temperature range: E-OBS
- total precipitation amount: E-OBS
- mean sea level pressure: E-OBS
- total cloud cover: CRU

Figure 3: Schematic overview of the subregions. (also called 'PRUDENCE regions' named after a former EU project).

Table 5: Definition of geographical dimensions of the subregions in degrees.

Area	West	East	South	North
BI – British Isles	-10	2	50	59
IP - Iberian Peninsula	-10	3	36	44
FR – France	-5	6	44	50
ME – Mid-Europe	2	16	48	55
SC –Scandinavia	5	30	55	70
AL – Alps	5	15	44	48
MD – Mediterranean	3	25	36	44
EA – Eastern Europe	16	30	44	55

Since some years the **ETOOOL and ETOOOL-VIS** have been developed to evaluate standard COSMO-CLM output. Within the last 1,5 years the tools have been extended by few community members and they are now in use to evaluate the latest model version and form the basis for the decision on the recommended model version and the associated namelist setting.

The tools are cshell-based with CDO³ applications, include NCL⁴ code for plotting and are designed with user friendliness in mind. BSS-plotting includes R-code. Daily and monthly means for mean, minimum and maximum temperature as well as for precipitation are derived and interpolated from the original model grid to the grid of the E-OBS observational dataset (version EOBSv10.0). For the interpolation of temperature, a height correction has been applied using a standard mean correction of 0.65K/100m. Additionally, cloud fraction is interpolated to the CRU data grid. ETOOOL creates statistics over the subregions and evaluates them against the observation data sets mentioned above.

ETOOOL-VIS creates basic plots from the calculated values in the ETOOOL to show deviations to the observations as spatial fields, monthly biases averaged or seasonal Taylor-diagrams over the subregions. The figures are created in EPS-file format, and also combined in PDFs.

ETOOOL-VIS allows the combination of single or several simulations in one Figure. This makes an inter comparison of more than or one or two simulations possible.

Whenever a reference run, sensitivity run or final run was finished, the ETOOOL and ETOOOL-VIS has been applied to the standard output. The Figures has been uploaded to the wiki and discussed by the participants.

³ Climate Data Operators <https://code.zmaw.de/projects/cdo>

⁴ NCAR Command Language <https://www.ncl.ucar.edu>

ETOOOL (based on csh and CDO)

Figure 4: Overview on the ETOOL-processes

2.2. Phase 1 – single parameter testing

In the first phase, it was decided to start with one reference simulation and a list of possible parameters to test in sensitivity runs in comparison to this reference simulation. Here, only one parameter at a time should be varied. In phase 2, combinations of different parameters, that have shown to be of interest in phase 1, are tested.

Reference simulations

... at DKRZ

As described in section 2.1, the simulations are conducted over the CORDEX-EU domain with a grid spacing of 0.44°. The forcing data was prepared once on the DKRZ computer and used by all participants for consistency reasons. This data, the configuration of the reference simulation with COSMO-CLM and all other relevant information was available via the RedC wiki page and/or at the DKRZ common disk space.

... at other machines

All those who did their sensitivity simulations on another computer machine than the blizzard at DKRZ had to repeat the reference simulation and compare their sensitivity results relative to their respective reference simulation for consistency reasons. In the end, runs on 6 different machines were carried out. The reference simulation has the identifier CON502, the reference runs on the other machines have an addon indicating the computer centre, respectively (see *Table 6* and *Table 7*). Additionally, ETHZ set up a small ensemble of 6 reference simulations on the same machine, but shifting the date of initialization each by 1 day.

Table 6: Simulations identifier of individual reference runs at different computing systems

Table 7: Simulations identifier of individual reference runs for the ensemble carried out by ETHZ at the CSCS.

IDs for CON502 at individual institutes
CON502(_DKRZ)
CON502_KUL
CON502_CSCS
CON502_LIST
CON502_DWD
CON502_LRZ

IDs for CON502 ensemble at ETHZ
CON502_CSCS(_mem1)
CON502_CSCS_mem2
CON502_CSCS_mem3
CON502_CSCS_mem4
CON502_CSCS_mem5
CON502_CSCS_mem6

A short investigation of this ensemble revealed no significant differences outside general internal model variability. No systematic differences between the ensemble on different computer systems and an ensemble on the same system were found, see *Figure 5* as an example. *Figure 6* demonstrates that the huge deviations between the ensemble members in the 5 year means are systematically reduced with increasing simulation length (20 year means).

Figure 5: Differences to the reference simulation for the simulations of T_{2M} at the different systems (left) and the different members of the CSCS ensemble. Reference simulation is the $CON502_CSCS(mem1)$.

Figure 6: Differences to the reference simulation as yearly cycle of precipitation for the convergence of simulations at the same system but for 20 years (left) and 5 years simulations (right).

Setup of the sensitivity runs

A list with possible sensitivity runs was compiled with a priority assigned to each option (see Section 2.1). From this, each participant could choose their contribution. In total, 60 sensitivity simulations were conducted in this phase (see *Table 8* for examples). An overview of the simulations is presented in *Figure 9*. Roughly, they can be grouped regarding aspects of dynamics and numerics (parameters `itype_fast_waves`, `itheta_adv`, `dt`, `y_scalar_advect`, `y_vert_adv_dyn`, `hd_corr_*`, `lspecnudge/nincsn`, `itype_bbc_w`), physics

(parameters `itype_heatcond`, `itype_aerosol`, `lmulti_snow`, `lstomata`, `lemiss`, `itype_albedo`, `itype_root`, `llake`, `itype_hydbound`, `limpltkediff`, `ltkesso`, `itype_sher`, `ltkecon`, `tkhmin`, `icldm_rad`, `itype_wcld`, `itype_evsl`), changes in the external parameters such as vegetation and land use and the distribution of vertical levels (parameter `vccord`).

Table 8: Overview of simulations carried out in Phase1 of COPAT. Only namelist parameters deviating from the reference simulation CON502 settings are listed. Blue (pink) background denotes configuration with positive (negative) impacts on the results.

Simulation identifier	changed namelist parameters	Comments
CON506	<code>itype_fast_waves=2</code>	using also <code>itype_bbc_w = 114</code>
CON507	<code>itheta_adv=1</code>	
CON510	<code>itheta_adv=2</code>	using <code>dt=72s</code>
CON511	<code>itype_heatcond=2</code>	using <code>COSMO_5.0_clm2</code>
tegen	<code>itype_aerosol=2</code> (Tegen)	
CON552	<code>itype_aerosol=2</code> (Aerocom)	
macc	<code>itype_aerosol=2</code> (MACC II)	
CON509	<code>lmulti_snow=T</code>	using <code>dt=72s</code> and <code>COSMO_5.0_clm2</code>
CON509a	<code>dt=72</code>	using <code>COSMO_5.0_clm2</code>
CON512	<code>y_scalar_advect=BOTT2_STRANG</code>	
CON513	<code>y_scalar_advect=BOTT4</code>	using <code>nboundlines=4</code>
CON521	<code>y_scalar_advect=BOTT4_STRANG</code>	using <code>nboundlines=4</code>
CON514	<code>y_scalar_advect=vanLeer</code>	
CON515	<code>y_scalar_advect=vanLeer_STRANG</code>	
CON517	<code>y_scalar_advect=SL3_MF</code>	
CON518	<code>y_scalar_advect=SL3_SFD</code>	
CON519	<code>y_scalar_advect=PPM</code>	using <code>nboundlines=4</code>
CON520	<code>y_scalar_advect=PPM_STRANG</code>	using <code>nboundlines=4</code>
stomata	<code>lstomata=T</code>	
emiss	<code>lemiss=T</code>	
CON503	<code>itype_albedo=2</code>	
CON504	<code>itype_albedo=3</code>	
CON505	<code>itype_albedo=4</code>	
CON522	<code>y_vert_adv_dyn=expl</code>	
CON523	<code>y_vert_adv_dyn=impl3</code>	
CON516	<code>itype_root=2</code>	
lake	<code>llake=T</code>	
aquifer	<code>itype_hydbound=3</code>	
CON536	<code>hd_corr_trcr_in=1.0</code>	
CON537	<code>hd_corr_trcr_bd=1.0</code>	

CON524	hd_corr_u_in=0.0	
CON530	hd_corr_u_bd=0.0	
CON531	hd_corr_u_bd=1.0	
CON532	hd_corr_t_in=1.0	
CON533	hd_corr_t_bd=1.0	
CON534	hd_corr_p_in=1.0	
CON535	hd_corr_p_bd=1.0	
CON546	nincsn=1, lspecnudge=T	
CON546b	nincsn=10, lspecnudge=T	
CON547	limpltkediff=T	
CON548	ltkesso=T	
CON549	itype_sher=2	
CON550	itype_sher=3	
CON551	ltkecon=T	
CON525	itype_bbc_w=0	
CON526	itype_bbc_w=2	
CON527	itype_bbc_w=3	
CON528	itype_bbc_w=4	
CON529	itype_bbc_w=5	
globcover	GLOBCOVER landuse data set	in EXTPAR, instead of GLC2000
CON553	ECOCLIMAP landuse data set	in EXTPAR, instead of GLC2000
heise	Heise lookup table for landuse data	in EXTPAR, instead of Ritter
ndvi	MODIS climatology based seasonal cycle of LAI and PLCOV	in EXTPAR
hwsd	Harmonized world soil database	in EXTPAR, instead of Digital Soil MAP of the World (FAO)
tkhmin	tkhmin=0.4 (from 0.35)	
CON554	icldm_rad=2	
CON555	itype_wcld=1	
CON556	itype_evsl=3	
CON557	vcoord.f90	using dz top reduced from 1900 m to 1620 m and int2lm NPX=3, NPY=6
CON558	vcoord.f90; ke_tot=50	using dz top reduced from 1900 m to 1620 m and int2lm NPX=3, NPY=6

For the post processing, all simulations were analyzed using the ETOOL and ETOOL-VIS software. With this, identical plots were produced, which could easily be compared. In the following, only results from those experiments, which show some significant impact are discussed.

The evaluation of former model versions of COSMO-CLM over the PRUDENCE regions showed some systematic model deficiencies with respect to surface temperature and precipitation. The diurnal temperature range is

underestimated, particularly in the semi-arid regions around the Mediterranean Sea. In some of the regions there is a warm bias in summer, and/or a slight cold and moist bias in spring.

In order to reduce these model biases, the new set-up of the model should have the following aims: Keep more water in the ground by reducing the evapotranspiration in winter and spring. As a consequence, the cold and moist biases in spring may be reduced. By keeping more soil water during spring and early summer, there may be more water left in the ground in late summer. This may allow for a higher evapotranspiration in summer which can reduce the warm and dry biases in this season over the Mediterranean and the Iberian Peninsula.

Results for the most promising simulations

CON506	itype_fast_waves=2	(in CON502 itype_fast_waves=1)	using also itype_bbc_w = 114
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This switch describes how the fast waves processes are treated by the model. itype_fast_waves=1 is the old fast waves solver which is not recommended to be used anymore. The newer fast waves solver for itype_fast_waves=2 uses a strong conservation form. This allows the model to better deal with steep orography, which can be beneficial for the simulation of precipitation.

CON511	itype_heatcond=2	(in CON502 itype_heatcond =1)	
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This switch describes how the soil thermal conductivity is computed. The underlying idea is that a wet soil has a high conductivity, a dry soil a low one. For itype_heatcond=1, the conductivity is constant in the vertical and in time, representing a soil of medium wetness. For itype_heatcond=2, the conductivity depends on the soil water content following Johansen (1975). For a detailed study on this, see Schulz et al. (2016).

One positive effect of this is that in bare soil dominated regions which are dry the diurnal amplitude of the simulated surface temperature is increased. This applies particularly to the Mediterranean and the Iberian Peninsula. This can improve the simulated 2-m temperature, particularly in terms of its bias.

CON513	y_scalar_advect=BOTT4	(in CON502 y_scalar_advect=BOTT2)	
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With this switch the scheme for the advection of scalar variables is selected. BOTT4 is favourable compared to BOTT2 because it provides a higher accuracy. But, it increases the computational costs by 10—15%, which appears to be too much for the improvement gained.

CON504	itype_albedo=3	(in CON502 itype_albedo=1)	
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This switch describes how the surface albedo is determined. For itype_albedo=1, it is set depending on land use. Additionally, a correction for soil moisture and snow cover is applied. For itype_albedo=3, an annual cycle of the surface albedo is specified based on the MODIS albedo. This is a satellite remote sensing product. In principle, the latter should be more realistic and therefore provide a better annual cycle of available energy at the land surface and therefore an improved simulation of the surface temperature. A drawback can be that this option does not allow for a feedback from soil moisture.

CON524	hd_corr_u_in=0.0	(in CON502 hd_corr_u_in=0.2500)	
CON530	hd_corr_u_bd=0.0	(in CON502 hd_corr_u_bd=0.2500)	

The recommendation by DWD, with respect to the numerics, is to choose as little horizontal diffusion as possible for wind speed components, as long as the model simulation stays stable. Less horizontal diffusion better keeps the distribution of the respected quantity and therefore allows for a more accurate solution.

CON526	itype_bbc_w=2	(in CON502 itype_bbc_w=1)	
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With this switch the scheme for the bottom boundary condition for the vertical wind speed is selected. This can have an implicit effect on the simulation of the surface turbulent heat fluxes. But it is not clear a priori which scheme may be most beneficial, this is more a matter of model tuning.

CON554	icldm_rad=2	(in CON502 icldm_rad=4)	
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This switch selects which diagnostic scheme for the sub-grid scale clouds is used. The schemes here are humidity based. They determine how the sub-grid scale clouds are formed when the air humidity is still below saturation. But it is exactly not clear which formulation may be most beneficial in the model.

CON556	itype_evsl=3	(in CON502 itype_evsl=2)	
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This switch describes how the bare soil evaporation is computed. For itype_evsl=2, the bare soil evaporation is calculated based on BATS (Dickinson 1984). This implementation in COSMO has large systematic model errors. The bare soil evaporation is highly overestimated under medium-wet to wet conditions, and underestimated under medium-dry to dry conditions. The overestimation leads to a drying-out of the soil and moist and cold biases of the near-surface atmosphere over many of the PRUDENCE regions, mainly in late winter and spring. The underestimation leads to dry and warm biases, particularly over the Mediterranean and the Iberian Peninsula in summer.

For itype_evsl=3, a formulation is applied which substantially reduces the overestimation of the bare soil evaporation. As described before, this can reduce the moist and cold biases in spring, as well as the dry and warm biases in summer, particularly over the Mediterranean and the Iberian Peninsula.

2.3. Phase 2 – combined parameter testing

Setup simulations

Starting with the most promising parameters found in Phase1, different simulations were conducted combining these options. The aim of this was, to test if the effects of the different parameters are additive and to find a parameter combination which performs best. During Phase2 further combinations of parameters were necessary to judge over new parameter settings introduced by incoming information. The parameters of the simulations performed in Phase2 are shown in *Table 9*. The rest of the set-up is identical to the CON502 as described in Section 2.1. The Tuning parameters (e.g. tkhmin) were kept constant (default values) for these simulations, because the optimisation of these parameters is part of Phase3.

Table 9: Overview of the simulations carried out in Phase2 of COPAT. Only namelist parameters deviating from CON502 settings are listed. Parameters in bold denote ‘new’ settings compared to the simulations above.

Simulation identifier	Changed namelist parameters	Comments
CON601	y_scalar_advect = BOTT4	

	itype_albedo = 3 nboundlines = 4	
CON602	y_scalar_advect = BOTT4 nboundlines = 4 itype_evsl = 3 itype_heatcond = 2	
CON603	ltkesso = T lstomata = T itype_evsl = 3 itype_heatcond = 2	requires new int2lm with lstomata=T
CON604	itype_heatcond = 2 yscalar_advect = BOTT4 nboundlines = 4 hd_cor_u_in = 0 hd_cor_u_bd = 0 itype_bbc_2 = 2 itype_fast_waves = 1 itype_evsl = 3 iddm_rad = 2 itype_albedo = 3	itype_bbc_w = 2 needs to be set together with itype_fast_waves=1 additional ALB_DIF fields merged to the int2lm fields of CON502
CON605	itype_evsl = 3 itype_albedo = 3 hd_corr_t_in = 1.0 hd_corr_t_bd = 1.0	
CON606	itype_evsl = 3 itype_heatcond = 2 hd_corr_u_in = 0 hd_corr_u_bd = 0 itype_albedo = 2	
CON607	itype_evsl = 3 itype_heatcond = 2 itype_albedo = 2	
CON608	itype_evsl = 3 itype_heatcond = 2 itype_albedo = 2 itype_root = 2	incl itype_rootdp = 4 in int2lm

Results

The Brier-Skill Scores for T_2M, total precipitation, minimum and maximum 2-meter air temperature are shown in *Figure 7* and *Figure 8*. From the results of the simulations CON601 – CON606, CON602 was the most favourite set-up. In general, most simulations showed very similar results, only the CON603 simulation showed a strong warm bias and produced remarkable outlying Brier-Skill-Scores.

The set-ups CON604 and CON605 were not chosen, because the itype_albedo = 3 option does not allow for feedback from soil-moisture, as a total albedo is prescribed. In addition, the CON605 set-up uses large values for the horizontal diffusion. The recommendation from DWD, with respect to the numerics, was to choose as less horizontal diffusion as possible.

Brier Skill Scores Ref: CON502, OBS: EOBS-v10.0/CRU3.2
BSS T_2M versus BSS TOT_PREC

Figure 7: Brier-Skill Score Plots for 2m air temperature (T_{2M}) against total precipitation (TOT_PREC). The dots show the mean values as average over all regions and the size of the crosses the minimum and maximum values for these regions. The stars show the values for Middle Europe.

Brier Skill Scores Ref: CON502, OBS: EOBS-v10.0/CRU3.2
BSS TMAX_2M versus BSS TMIN_2M

Figure 8: As Figure 7 but for maximum T_{2M} versus minimum T_{2M} .

The favoured CON602 set-up, however, uses the BOTT4 scheme for the advection of scalar variables, which increases the computational costs by 10–15 % in comparison to the BOTT2 scheme. The comparable counterpart without the BOTT4 scheme, CON606, however, produced results slightly worse than then CON602. To investigate if these differences between the CON602 and CON606 are caused by the switched off horizontal diffusion, a further simulation CON607 was performed. The set-up is identical with CON606, despite the changes for the horizontal diffusion.

This simulation produced results very similar to the CON602, especially because of the reduced computational costs this set-up was chosen for the Phase 3.

In addition, the simulation CON608 was carried out, using `itype_root = 2`. This replaces the block of roots, all having the same length, by an exponential root profile, generally reducing the uptake of soil water by the

vegetation. Compared to CON607, this reduces the moist bias in spring in some of the evaluation domains. In particular, the warm and dry biases in summer over the Mediterranean and the Iberian Peninsula are reduced considerably.

2.4. Phase 3 – tuning

The objective calibration was the last step taken in the COPAT project to find a recommended configuration of the COSMO-CLM regional climate model that was based on COSMO 5.0 after, in earlier phases of the project, model options had been tested systematically to come to a set of options that produced the most promising results, i.e. climatology with the smallest biases.

The objective calibration with the method of Bellprat et al. (2012) consists of the 5 main steps listed here:

- Choice of the sensitive tuning parameters which will be used in the calibration
- Performing the simulations over the range of the tuning parameters.
- Building of a meta-model
- Definition of a performance metric
- Exploration of parameter space for optimal set of parameters

The individual steps of calibration will be addressed separately in the sections below

Choice of sensitive tuning parameters

The choice of the sensitive tuning parameters is based on the work of Bellprat et al. (2016). Four of the parameters used for the calibration were preexisting tuning parameters, two were model internal parameters and two were introduced especially for the calibration by changing the code of the COSMO model. This new model version became COSMO5.0_clm5. All the parameters can be set in the “TUNING” block of the namelist input file INPUT_ORG.

As can be seen, the tuning parameters, listed in Table 10, are from different parameterization schemes and should therefore be independent.

Table 10: List of tuning parameters and their prescribed range [minimum value; **default value**; maximum value].

Parameter name	Description of the parameter	Tested range and default value
rlam_heat	Scalar resistance for sensible and latent heat fluxes in the laminar surface layer	[0.1;1;5]
entr_sc	Entrainment rate for shallow convection [m^{-3}]	[$3 \cdot 10^{-5}$; $3 \cdot 10^{-4}$; $3 \cdot 10^{-3}$]
tkhmin	Minimal vertical turbulent diffusion rate [m^2s^{-1}]	[0.1; 1 ; 2]
qi0	Threshold for conversion cloud ice to snow	[0 ; $5 \cdot 10^{-5}$; 10^{-4}]
uc1	Parameter controlling the vertical variation of critical relative humidity for sub-grid cloud formation	[0; 0.8 ; 1.6]
radfac	Fraction of cloud water and ice considered by radiation scheme	[0.3; 0.5 ; 0.9]
fac_rootdp2	Uniform factor for root depth field	[0.5; 1 ; 1.5]
soilhyd	Factor for the hydraulic conductivity and diffusivity	[0.1;1;10]

Performing the simulation with changed parameters

The simulation necessary for the calibration consist of a reference simulation, simulations where 1 parameter is changed to either the minimum or maximum value of the physical meaningful range and simulations where two parameters are changed to either of the extreme values. Each of those simulation is driven by ERAinterim and covers the years 1979-1983. All simulations use the same initial and boundary data. Initial soil moisture is taken from a twenty-year long climatology from a previous simulation with the reference configuration. The total number of simulations that need to be performed for such a setup with N parameters is as follows:

1. Reference simulation with all parameters at the default value (1 simulation)
2. Sensitivity simulations with one of the N parameters set to either extreme value ($2 \cdot N$ simulations)
3. Sensitivity simulations where 2 different parameters are set to either extreme value ($N \cdot (N-1)/2$ pairs with 4 possible combinations => $2 \cdot N \cdot (N-1)$ simulations)
4. A total of $1 + 2 \cdot N \cdot N$ simulations (for N=8: **129 simulations**)

For each of these simulations the target values (monthly mean values for the climate parameters **T_2M**, **TOT_PREC** and **CLCT** averaged over the 8 PRUDENCE domains) are determined in a post-processing step. That is $5(\text{years}) \cdot 12(\text{months}) \cdot 8(\text{regions}) \cdot 3(\text{climate parameters}) = 1440$ values.

Building of a meta-model

The next step is to build a meta-model that estimates the values of the climate parameters for each month and each PRUDENCE region as a function of the values of the calibration parameters, where the values of the calibration parameters are within the predefined range. In fact, there are 1440 individual meta-models that have the same functional structure. They are all calculated as a quadratic deviation from the reference state (all parameters assume their uncalibrated default values). For a calibration with 3 tuning parameters μ_1 , μ_2 and μ_3 this looks as follows:

$$\theta(\mu_1, \mu_2, \mu_3) = \theta_{ref} + a_1 \cdot \mu_1 + a_2 \cdot \mu_2 + a_3 \cdot \mu_3 + b_1 \cdot \mu_1^2 + b_2 \cdot \mu_2^2 + b_3 \cdot \mu_3^2 + c_1 \cdot \mu_1 \cdot \mu_2 + c_2 \cdot \mu_1 \cdot \mu_3 + c_3 \cdot \mu_2 \cdot \mu_3$$

The coefficients a_1 , a_2 and a_3 (linear terms), b_1 , b_2 and b_3 (quadratic terms) and c_1 , c_2 and c_3 (interaction terms) need then to be calculated based on the values of the simulations with the changed parameters. For N tuning parameters the number of unknown coefficients is $2 \cdot N + N \cdot (N-1)/2$. For 8 calibration parameters this amounts to 44 unknown coefficients. With the 128 simulations with changed tuning parameters we have an over-determined linear system that needs to be solved. A least square error method is used for this purpose.

Performance metric

To evaluate the individual simulations a performance metric, which delivers a single value for each simulation, is necessary. We use here the same performance metric that was also applied in the work of Bellprat et al. (2016) for the European continent. However, we are evaluating temperatures and precipitation against the E-OBS version 10 0.44deg rotated dataset, which matches the grid of the CORDEX simulation. For the evaluation of the cloud-cover data we use the same gridded dataset originating from CRU as was used in Bellprat et al. (2016). The difficulty is to bring together model bias values of different physical quantities and for different seasons. The approach taken here is, for each month of the simulation and each PRUDENCE region, to normalize the squared difference model - observation by the total uncertainties given by an estimate of the observation error, the interannual variability and an estimate of the internal variability of the model simulation. In mathematical language:

$$PI^2 = \frac{1}{12 \cdot R \cdot CV \cdot Y} \sum_{m=1}^{12} \sum_{r=1}^R \sum_{c=1}^{CV} \sum_{y=1}^Y \frac{(mod(y,m,r,c) - obs(y,m,r,c))^2}{(\sigma_{iv}(m,r,c) + \sigma_{iav}(m,r,c) + \sigma_{oerr}(m,r,c))^2}$$

Where r runs over all PRUDENCE regions, y over all 5 simulated years, m over the 12 months of the year and cover all $c=3$ evaluated climate parameters T_2M, TOT_PREC and CLCT. The uncertainty estimates that appear in the normalization term are as follows:

$\sigma_{iv}(m, r, c)$: estimate of internal variability based on 6-member ensemble covering 180 years.

$\sigma_{iav}(m, r, c)$: interannual variability based on E-OBS data for corresponding month, region and climate parameter.

$\sigma_{oerr}(m, r, c)$: estimate of observational uncertainty based on estimated values given by E-OBS or differences between independent data sets (CLCT).

To cast the score to the range 0 to 1, where 1 would be the perfect score we use for the final performance score

$$PS = e^{-0.5 \cdot PI^2}$$

Exploration of the parameter space to find optimal settings

The Matlab function *lhsdesign* with the criterion “correlation” was used to produce a set of 5 million combinations for the tuning parameters to sample the parameter space for the optimal combination of parameters. *Figure 9* shows the distribution of the achieved PS score for all of the 5 million sampled combinations. As can be seen in *Figure 9* only a relatively small fraction (0.15%) of the simulations achieves a better score than the reference simulation. The skill score of the reference simulation has a value of 0.8790, whereas the highest predicted value by the meta-model in the sample amounts to 0.9047.

Figure 9: Relative density of PS skill scores for all 5 million sampled calibration parameter combinations. The line labelled REF shows the value for the default setting of the parameters. The red line labelled OPT denotes the highest score achieved in the whole sample.

The sampled combination of tuning parameters which achieves the highest skill score, is summarized in *Table 11*.

Table 11: Optimized values of calibration parameters.

Calibration parameter	Optimized value
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rlam_heat	0.5249
entr_sc	1.86e⁻⁴
qi0	0.0
uc1	0.0626
tkhmin	0.35
fac_rootdp2	0.9
radfac	0.5
soilhyd	1.62

In Figure 10 the distribution of the values of the calibrated parameters with respect to the reference values can be seen. For qi0 and radfac the calibrated values coincide with the default values. For uc1 the default value seems to be at the high end of the range of values with high scores. The calibrated value of tkhmin is at the low end of the range of values with high scores.

Figure 10: Parameter density for the 0.1% combinations with the highest PS skill score. The gray vertical lines show the extreme values of the parameter range, the red line the default values used in the reference simulation. And the dashed black line the values for the parameter combination with the highest skill score. Note that for entr_sc and soilhyd the logarithm of the actual values is shown.

Control simulation with calibrated parameters

In the next step a simulation covering the period 1979-2000 with all calibration parameters set to their calibrated values was performed.

Figure 11 shows the effect of the calibration with respect to the bias of the climatological summer (JJA) 2-meter temperature based on E-OBS observation data for the period 1981-2000. It is evident that the calibration causes an overall cooling over the whole domain. This cooling is beneficial to all regions which overestimated the summer temperature in the uncalibrated simulation. However, the cooling is detrimental to the region north of 60° latitude, which was already too cold in the uncalibrated simulation.

In contrast to temperature the effect of the calibration on JJA total precipitation is minor (see *Figure 12*). The bias remains almost unchanged. A slight improvement may be visible over Eastern Europe. The same is also true for total cloud cover, which is not shown here.

The reduction of the bias shows also in the PS skill score, which for the calibrated simulation evaluated again for the period 1979-1983 amounts now to **0.8958**. This is slightly lower than value that was estimated by the meta-model (**0.9047**) but still 1.5% higher than the skill score of the uncalibrated configuration (**0.8790**).

The improvement is also visible in the seasonal cycles of the biases shown in *Figure 13*, *Figure 14* and . Please note that for total precipitation and total cloud cover the differences between the calibrated and the uncalibrated simulation mostly remain in the range of the internal variability or the observational uncertainty.

Figure 11: Model bias of the 2-meter temperature with respect to E-OBS observation values for the summer seasonal mean (JJA) for the average of the years 1981-2000 [K].

Figure 12: Model bias of the total precipitation with respect to E-OBS observational values for the summer seasonal mean (JJA) averaged over the years 1981-2000 [mm/day].

Figure 13: seasonal cycle of 2-meter temperature bias with respect to the E-OBS data averaged over the 8 PRUDENCE regions (British Islands(BI), Iberian Peninsula (IP), France (FR), Middle Europe (ME), Scandinavia (SC), Alpine region (AL), Mediterranean area (MD) and Eastern Europe (EA), see Figure 3). The blue lines show the results for the calibrated simulation, the red line the results for the uncalibrated simulation and the black line results for the configuration which was the starting point of the COPAT experiment.

BIAS CCLM - EOBS (TOT_PREC)

Figure 14: As Figure 13 but for total precipitation.

BIAS CCLM - CRU (CLCT)

Figure 15: As Figure 13 but for total cloud cover bias as compared to the CRU gridded climatology.

Final remarks on the tuning

It should be noted here that the final configuration which was presented at the CLM Assembly 2015 to be accepted as the recommended configuration at hydrostatic scales for the European domain (EURO-CORDEX domain) was slightly different to the configuration used in the calibration process. It was suggested by Jan-Peter Schulz that `itype_root=2` should be used in combination with `itype_evsl=3`. `itype_root=2` then also requires a time invariant root depth, i.e. `itype_rootdp=4` in `int2lm`. This suggestion was only made after the calibration work had been started and it was too late to include it in the process. But since the change of this switch alone showed a beneficial impact on the Brier Skill Score at the end of calibration an additional simulation was performed with `itype_root=2` and all calibration parameters set to the calibrated values except for `fac_rootdp2`, which remained at the default value of 1. This additional simulation achieved an even higher PS skill score of **0.8984** than the simulation with `itype_root=1`.

Even though the daily temperature range (DTR) is not used in the evaluation of the simulations during the calibration process, the resulting values in the calibrated simulation showed an improved skill for representing this quantity compared to the uncalibrated simulation.

Bellprat et al. (2016) found a significant improvement for the interannual variability of the summer mean temperature when using the calibrated set of parameters (see their *Figure 5*). In *Figure 16* it is shown that also as a result of the calibration for COSMO 5.0 this quantity is improved. However, this improvement is not quite as significant since the bias of the reference simulation is already considerably smaller than the bias of the reference in their paper.

It was also tested whether DTR could be directly included in the performance skill score PS as a 4th climate variable. From a technical point of view this can be achieved rather easily since `TMAX_2m` and `TMIN_2M` are also available from E-OBS. However, since the biases of DTR are much larger than those for `T_2M` and the normalization values are essentially of the same size the quadratic term in the numerator of the PI score favors improvements of DTR also at the expense of a deterioration of `T_2M`. Thus, it was decided to stay with the 3 climate parameters used in Bellprat et al. (2012).

`qi0` was used as a tuning parameter in this work. But as the results of the calibration procedure show, any change from the default value of 0.0 deteriorates the results. Similar results were also found in the CALMO project for NWP at the 1 km scale. Omitting this calibration parameter and also the parameter for root depth (which is set to the default value in the recommended configuration) would reduce the computational costs substantially (73 instead of 129 simulations needed).

The whole calibration was performed for a grid resolution of 0.44 degrees. However, we also performed a 30-years long simulation with the same calibration parameters for the EURO-CORDEX configuration at 18 km resolution. The biases for this simulation were very similar to the biases seen with the coarser resolution simulation. Thus, the calibrated values should also be usable for higher resolution simulations as long as they use parameterized convection.

Figure 16: Bias of interannual variability for summer season mean temperature [K] with respect to E-OBS for the period 1981-2000. The left panel shows the bias for the reference simulation and the right panel for the simulation with the calibrated parameters.

The calibration process improved the overall PS skill score of the cosmo5.0_clm6 based configuration for the EURO-CORDEX-044 domain by about 1.5%. This is not a dramatic improvement and leads to the conclusion that the uncalibrated model was already well tuned.

The main improvements can be seen in the 2-meter temperature bias, which is most notably decreased during summer in the southern and eastern parts of Europe. However, to the north of 60° latitude the negative temperature bias is increased (Figure 11 and Figure 13).

Total precipitation and cloud cover remain almost unchanged by the calibration (Figure 12, Figure 14, and).

The diurnal temperature range (not shown) and the interannual variability of mean summer temperature are also slightly improved (Figure 16) even though they hadn't been evaluated explicitly in the calibration process.

2.5. Phase 4 – final simulation at 0.165° resolution

Final simulation with best setup including tuning

Results

a) Mean annual cycles

The results of the simulation CON052 with the new model version 5.0 but a configuration nearly identical to the configuration of the former evaluation simulation with the old model version 4.8 are very similar to this old evaluation run (CON031) for the three temperature variables (T_2M, TMIN_2M and TMAX_2M) and total precipitation (TOT_PREC) in all 8 regions as *Figure 17 to 21* show. Stronger deviations occur for TMAX_2M (*Figure 20*) in some regions like FR and AL with the tendency to lower maximum values in CCLM 5.0 and for mean sea level pressure (PMSL in *Figure 21*) and total cloud cover (CLCT in *Figure 22*). The new model version with the new and optimized configuration (CON069) produces, however, an annual cycle of the 2-meter temperature (T_2M) which substantially differs from the two other simulations in nearly all regions except Scandinavia (SC). The former overestimation of summer temperatures is reduced and the sometimes too low spring temperatures are raised by more than 1 K. Overall, the seasonal course of the T_2M bias becomes flatter than in the previous evaluations with a pronounced underestimation of winter and spring temperatures and overestimation of summer and autumn temperatures.

The effect of the new model version and configuration on total precipitation is small as *Figure 18* demonstrates. The general tendencies of seasonal biases are conserved in the new evaluation simulation CON069. Only for Middle and Eastern Europe (ME and EA) the overestimation of springtime precipitation and for EA the late summer dryness are reduced. The strong bias over the Alpine region with values up to 40 mm/month is only weakly reduced by the new configuration.

A major deficit of all former model versions was that they substantially overestimated the daily minimum temperature (TMIN_2M) by partly several degrees and tended to underestimate the daily maximum temperature (TMAX_2M) which results in a general underestimation of the diurnal temperature range. With the new model version and configuration the strong positive bias of TMIN_2M is reduced (*Figure 19*) in particular over IP, FR, MD and FR and the too low monthly means of TMAX_2M (*Figure 20*) especially in winter are partly raised, with an improving effect of both modifications on the diurnal temperature range. But the overall deficit of a too low daily maximum temperature and a too high daily minimum temperature in the annual average still persists over nearly the whole model domain as can be seen in *Figure 23 (middle and lower panel)*.

The general shape of the annual cycle of mean sea level pressure (PMSL) bias is conserved in all three simulations (*Figure 21*) but the values are shifted by about 1 hPa. The new model version (CON052) and even more pronounced with the new configuration (CON069) systematically reduces the pressure values compared to old evaluation (CON031) by up to 2 hPa. This positively leads to a reduction of the positive winter bias but further deepens the negative depression in summer. Altogether, it has to be stated that the new version does not improve the pressure performance of the simulation.

BIAS CCLM - EOBS (T_2M)

Figure 17: Annual cycle of 2-meter temperature (T_{2M}) bias [K] with respect to the E-OBS data averaged over the 8 PRUDENCE regions (British Islands (BI), Iberian Peninsula (IP), France (FR), Middle Europe (ME), Scandinavia (SC), Alpine region (AL), Mediterranean area (MD) and Eastern Europe (EA)). The red lines (CON069) show the results for the simulation with the new model version CCLM5.0 and the optimized configuration, the blue lines (CON052) the results for the new model version with the configuration of the old evaluation run and the black lines (CON031) the results for the old evaluation run with CCLM4.8. with 0.165° grid resolution.

BIAS CCLM - EOBS (TOT_PREC)

Figure 18: As Figure 17 but for total precipitation TOT_PREC [mm/month].

BIAS CCLM - EOBS (TMIN_2M)

Figure 19: As Figure 17 but for 2-meter daily minimum temperature TMIN_2M [K].

BIAS CCLM - EOBS (TMAX_2M)

Figure 20: As Figure 17 but for 2-meter daily maximum temperature TMAX_2M [K].

BIAS CCLM - EOBS (PMSL)

Figure 21: As Figure 17 but for mean sea level pressure PMSL [hPa].

BIAS CCLM - CRU (CLCT)

Figure 22: As Figure 17 but for total cloud cover CLCT with unit fraction and compared with CRU data.

The total cloud cover (CLCT) (*Figure 22*) differs between the three simulations by several percent. The general shape of the annual cycle is more or less conserved. But the new version tends to increase the cloud cover especially in summer so that the bias partly increases compared to the old version. It has to be considered, however, that we cannot really assess the quality of the reference data from CRU as we have no experience with alternative data in this case.

b) Spatial distributions of annual means

The next series of figures shows the spatial distribution of the 20 years annual mean difference between the new evaluation simulation (CON069) and the corresponding reference data (CRU for CLCT and EOBS for all others) for the six evaluation parameters. The bias of the annual mean of the 2-meter daily mean temperature in *Figure 23* (upper panel) shows a variation in sign across Europe. The temperature in northern and northeastern Europe is generally underestimated whereas it is overestimated by up to several degrees in southeastern Europe. The middle and western parts of Europe show a non-uniform bias varying around zero by less than one degree. The Spanish Peninsula is dominated in the new version by a weak negative temperature bias. The influence of the boundary zone becomes noticeable by a curved band with positive temperature deviations along the eastern domain boundary.

The annual mean of the daily minimum temperature (*Figure 23* middle panel) is too high nearly everywhere except the Norwegian coastal region and exceeds the reference temperature of the EOBS data by up to 5 K over the Balkans. The values of the daily maximum temperature (*Figure 23* lower panel) are simulated too low everywhere in Europe with some local exceptions only in southern Europe. The maximum underestimation with values up to -5 K occurs in Scandinavia and northeastern Europe. This illustrates, that it is still necessary to further improve the diurnal cycle of the surface and surface near temperatures in the upcoming model versions.

In the area from northwestern to southwestern Europe - the land regions towards the western domain boundary - the mean annual precipitation sum is dominated by a substantial deficit of up to more than -300 mm/year (dark red color range in *Figure 24*). In some parts of Central Europe, especially the Alpine area, and the eastern and northern parts of Europe the simulated annual precipitation exceeds the reference values of the EOBS data everywhere with only some local exceptions and reaches its maximum deviations with more than 300 mm/year (dark blue color range in *Figure 24*) along the Norwegian coastline and the eastern domain boundary, the so called "outflow" boundary. For the central part of Europe, the precipitation deficits in the north western area and the overestimations in eastern and southern areas nearly compensate each other as well as the general overestimation in winter and early spring and the underestimation in summer (see panel ME in *Figure 18*) so that the annual and spatial mean of this region shows only a weak precipitation bias in total.

The simulated annual mean sea level pressure (*Figure 24* middle panel) is generally too low. The deviation increases towards the center of the model domain and reaches maximum values of about -2.5 hPa. *Figure 24* demonstrates that the new version with the recommended configuration underestimates surface pressure in all seasons with a maximum deviation in summer months in all eight regions. The reason for this very systematic behavior of the model is not clear but seems to be related to the time step dependency of the simulations which is currently investigated by the SUPTECH working group of the CLM community.

Figure 23: Horizontal distribution of the annual mean bias for the 2-meter daily mean (T_{2M}), minimum ($TMIN_{2M}$) and maximum ($TMAX_{2M}$) temperatures [K] of the new evaluation simulation CON069 with respect to E-OBS for the period 1980-2000.

Run CON069 -- Difference CCLM-EOBS (TOT_PREC) -- 1981-2000

Run CON069 -- Difference CCLM-EOBS (PMSL) -- 1981-2000

Run CON069 -- Difference CCLM-CRU (CLCT) -- 1981-2000

Figure 24: As Figure 12 but for total precipitation (TOT_PREC) [mm/year], mean sea level pressure (PMSL) [hPa] and total cloud cover (CLCT) with unit fraction.

Finally, the annual mean total cloud cover (CLCT in *Figure 24* lower panel) is overestimated by 10 to 20 % (percentage points) in northern and northeastern Europe and underestimated by more than -10 % in some parts of southwestern Europe and the British Islands. In the remaining areas the deviation in the annual mean is clearly less than 10 % partly due to stronger but sign changing variations throughout the year (see *Figure 24*).

Further results for seasonal values can be found in the supplementary material⁵.

c) Taylor diagrams of temporal variability

Figure 25 shows Taylor diagrams of 2-meter air temperature (**T_2M**) with respect to the E-OBS data averaged over each of the 8 PRUDENCE regions for the three different models and model configurations CON031, CON52 and CON069. With respect to CON031 and CON052 the final configuration and the new model version CON069 improves the standard deviation compared to the observed one from E-OBS. A general increase of temporal correlation can be seen especially over the sub regions FR, IP and ME. The results for both simulations with the old configuration CON031 and CON052 are very similar, although the trend to a better representation of the standard deviation with the model version is visible. The quite dominant overestimation of the standard deviation in mean temperature during summer in CON031 and CON052 has been reduced in CON069.

The temporal variability in the total precipitation amounts (**TOT_PREC**) (*Figure 26*) in CON069 is reduced, which leads often to an improvement in the standard deviation compared to CON052. In the new model version with new setup (CON069) an improvement mostly in both standard deviation and temporal correlation can be detected. For certain regions like British Isles (BI), Mediterranean (MD), the Alps (AL), Eastern Europe (EA) and Scandinavia (SC) the temporal correlation is increased in CON069 compared to the other simulations.

The results for the minimum air temperature (**TMIN_2M**) (see *Figure 27*) are very similar to the results for T_2M. The standard deviation in time shows a better representation of the observed values in CON069. Compared to the two simulations CON031 and CON052, the new model version and the optimised setup in CON069 leads to an increase of temporal correlation in the regions France (FR), Mid-Europe (ME), Scandinavia (SC) and Eastern Europe (EA).

In all regions and most seasons there is an improved temporal variability in the maximum air temperature values (**TMAX_2M**) (see *Figure 28*). Very good results can be detected for the regions EA, MD, ME and BI, where CON069 show mostly better results for both the standard deviation and the temporal correlation compared to the other two simulations. In all regions the results for the summer maximum temperature can be improved through a slight increase in correlation values, but especially through the better representation of the temporal variability.

For mean sea level pressure (**PMSL**) the correlation is quite high compared the other meteorological parameters evaluated in the COPAT (see *Figure 29*). Lowest correlation values can be detected for summer season and especially in the regions AL, EA, MD, FR and ME. The results for mean sea level pressure for the combinations of model version and model setup are quite similar. Just in summer there is an increase of the standard deviation in CON069, which leads to a little deterioration compared to the other two simulations.

⁵ Supplementary Material to the Evaluation Report COSMO-CLM5.0: CON069_DIFF_all_fields_1981-2000_REG9_seasonal-maps.pdf

The comparison of total cloud cover (**CLCT**) of the different model runs to the observed ones from CRU (see *Figure 30*) is quite critical, as the quality of the CRU CLCT data might not be sufficient. The correlation might therefore be lower than expected with values below 0.9 for most seasons and regions.

Figure 25: Taylor diagrams of 2-meter temperature with respect to the E-OBS data averaged over the 8 PRUDENCE regions (British Islands (BI), Iberian Peninsula (IP), France (FR), Middle Europe (ME), Scandinavia (SC), Alpine region (AL), Mediterranean area (MD) and Eastern Europe (EA)). The red dots (CON069) show the results for the simulation with the new model version CCLM5.0 and the optimized configuration, the blue dots (CON052) the results for the new model version with the configuration of the old evaluation run and the black dots (CON031) the results for the old evaluation run with CCLM4.8. Different numbers indicate different time periods within a year. The correlation indicates the temporal variability.

Temporal variability for TOT_PREC

Figure 26: As Figure 25 but for total precipitation amount.

Temporal variability for TMIN_2M

Figure 27: As Figure 25 but for 2-meter daily minimum temperature.

Temporal variability for TMAX_2M

Figure 28: As Figure 25 but for 2-meter daily maximum temperature.

Temporal variability for PMSL

Figure 29: As Figure 25 but for mean sea level pressure.

Temporal variability for CLCT

Figure 30: As Figure 25 but for total cloud cover and compared with the CRU data.

d) Taylor diagrams of spatial variability

The results for the air temperature (**T_2M**) of the different simulations among each other, but also with respect to regions or seasons are very similar. CON069 does not show a clear improvement compared to the results for CON052 or CON031 (see *Figure 31*).

The spatial correlation of the time-averaged total precipitation pattern (**TOT_PREC**) is in general lower with values between 0.5 and 0.9 than the time-correlation of the spatially averaged total precipitation (see *Figure 26* and *Figure 32*). In most of the different regions the new model version with the new model configuration CON069 leads to a slight increase in correlation values.

Again, the results from the different simulations for the minimum (**TMIN_2M**) and maximum temperature (**TMAX_2M**) are - similar as for T_2M - very close together (see *Figure 31*, *Figure 33*, and *Figure 34*). For the minimum temperature, there is no model simulation which performs better than the others. The better results for the maximum temperature in CON069 compared to CON031 and CON052 can be seen for the region of FR, IP and EA, with no change in the spatial correlation but with a better representation of the observed spatial variability.

The spatial pattern of the mean sea level pressure (**PMSL**) is not well represented in any of the model simulations (see *Figure 35*). Biggest problems occur for the regions AL, MD and EA. There is no model simulation which performs best among the three. Highest correlation values can be seen in the regions BI, ME and SC, lowest in the regions IP and MD.

As already stated before, the cloud cover (**CLCT**) is quite difficult to evaluate. The different model simulations behave similar, especially in the regions AL, ME, FR and MD (see *Figure 36*).

Spatial variability for T_2M

Figure 31: Taylor diagrams of 2-meter temperature with respect to the E-OBS data averaged over the 8 PRUDENCE regions (British Islands (BI), Iberian Peninsula (IP), France (FR), Middle Europe (ME), Scandinavia (SC), Alpine region (AL), Mediterranean area (MD) and Eastern Europe (EA)). The red dots (CON069) show the results for the simulation with the new model version CCLM5.0 and the optimized configuration, the blue dots (CON052) the results for the new model version with the configuration of the old evaluation run and the black dots (CON031) the results for the old evaluation run with CCLM4.8. Different numbers indicate different time periods within a year. The correlation indicates the temporal variability.

Spatial variability for TOT_PREC

Figure 32: As Figure 31 but for total precipitation.

Spatial variability for TMIN_2M

Figure 33: As Figure 31 but for 2-meter daily minimum temperature.

Spatial variability for TMAX_2M

Figure 34: As Figure 31 but for 2-meter daily maximum temperature.

Figure 35: As Figure 31 but for mean sea level pressure.

Figure 36: As Figure 31 but for total cloud cover and compared with the CRU data.

e) combined Brier Skill Scores

Figure 37 and *Figure 38* show the combined Brier Skill Scores (BSS) from two parameters each. The first is combining daily mean air temperature and daily precipitation amount and the second the daily minimum and maximum air temperature. Colours indicate the different model simulations. The reference simulation is CON031, the former recommended model version with old model setup. For the differences in the model simulations including configurations see *Table 1*. The symbols represent the results for the different regions and the entire domain (9. ENT). If a simulation performs better than the reference CON031, the BSS is positive.

CON052 is the new model version with old setup, CON067 the new model version with optimised setup from the first two COPAT-phases, CON069 is similar to CON067 but includes the tuning. In *Figure 37* the improvement from one simulation to the other is clearly visible. Where CON052 performs quite similar to the reference CON031- the old model version with old model setup -, CON067 shows already a clear improvement in both temperature and precipitation for most of the sub regions. In CON067 for the regions EA and ME the performance is better than for CON031 in the total precipitation but not for the mean temperature. For Scandinavia it is the other way round, there is no added value in the total precipitation but in temperature. CON069 shows a clear improvement regarding the temperature, but also in total precipitation. There are only the sub region Scandinavia and the entire domain, where the skill in temperature is about the same in CON052 and CON031. In the region IP, the Iberian Peninsula, there is no skill for precipitation, but a strong positive BSS for the temperature.

Comparing the BSS for daily minimum and maximum temperature or the daily cycle, CON052 performs very similar to the reference CON031 (see *Figure 38*). In CON067 the maximum temperature is better represented than in the reference for all sub regions. Instead, the minimum temperature is better in the reference for all sub regions, but not for the entire domain. After the tuning the picture changes. In CON069 for most regions there is still a positive BSS in the maximum temperature, but also a positive BSS in the minimum temperature. Only for Scandinavia there is no positive BSS in the maximum temperature, the performance for the whole domain is similar to the reference, and the sub regions Alps – AL – and British Isles have a negative BSS for the minimum temperature, but a positive BSS for the maximum temperature. The change between the tuning and no tuning is clearly visible.

Brier Skill Scores Ref: CON031, OBS: EOBS-v10.0
 BSS T_2M versus BSS TOT_PREC

Figure 37: Combined Brier Skill Scores for T_2M and TOT_PREC for the simulations CON052, CON067 and CON069. CON031 works as the reference simulation.

Brier Skill Scores Ref: CON031, OBS: EOBS-v10.0
 BSS TMAX_2M versus BSS TMIN_2M

Figure 38: Combined Brier Skill Scores for TMIN_2M and TMAX_2M for the simulations CON052, CON067 and CON069. CON031 works as the reference simulation.

e) spatial distribution of Brier Skill Scores

BSS – CON 069 vs ref: CON031 --- T_2M

BSS – CON 069 vs ref: CON031 --- TMIN_2M

BSS – CON 069 vs ref: CON031 --- TMAX_2M

BSS – CON 069 vs ref: CON031 --- TOT_PREC

BSS – CON 069 vs ref: CON031 --- PMSL

Figure 39: Spatial distribution of the Brier Skill Scores for the 2-meter mean, minimum and maximum air temperature, total precipitation, and mean sea level pressure.

2.6. Final Phase – recommended model version

Decision in the working group and presenting the results to the community

The results of the evaluation were first presented to the WG-Evaluation during the CCLM-Assembly in Luxembourg. As the WG-members agreed, the evaluated model version `cosmo5.0_clm6` was suggested to become the recommended community version.

Community decision on the new recommended model version

As the WG-EVAL can only suggest a model version to become the recommended version of COSMO-CLM, Klaus Keuler presented the main evaluation results to the plenary. Through the CCLM-Community Coordinator the plenary was invited to agree or disagree to the WG-suggestion to go for `COSMO5.0_clm6` as the new recommended model version. The CCLM-Community accepted this version to be the recommended version.

Meanwhile some further technical improvements have been introduced into the recommended version resulting in the new subversion `clm17`. Using the configuration of the standard evaluation presented in this report the results with this subversion do not change. Therefore, `COSMO5.0_clm17` can also be regarded as the recommended version.

Including a recommended namelist into the namelist tool

Beside the recommended version itself for Europe a recommended setup of the model has been defined during the process of evaluation. This namelist is now included in the namelist tool⁶ and is free for download or comparison with own namelists.

Evaluation report

This document is the final evaluation report of the model version `COSMO5.0_clm6`. It describes the evaluation process itself but also the most important results. The report supports the use of the recommended model version and serves as a reference for all future developments of the regional climate model COSMO-CLM.

Scientific publications

The procedure of COPAT, the Coordinated Parameter Testing, was presented as a poster or an invited talk with the title “COPAT- towards a recommended model version of COSMO-CLM” at:

- COSMO-User Seminar 2016, March in Offenbach
- EGU Assembly 2016, April in Vienna
- ICRC CORDEX 2016, Mai in Stockholm.
- COSMO-CLM Community Assembly

⁶ Comment from 20024/12: the namelist tool is currently not available, but when back in operation the links will be as before http://www.clm-community.eu/namelist-tool/namelist-tool_portal/namelists/cosmo_all/CCLM-EU165_5.0_clm6.txt and http://www.clm-community.eu/namelist-tool/namelist-tool_portal/index.htm?conf=cosmo_all)

Publication of the procedure in a scientific journal on the basis of this evaluation report was planned but never realised.

3. References

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